

Title: Assessment of rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases syndemic in Mayan-Yucatecan
Indigenous communities: A cross-sectional study

Supplementary image 1. Study area and participating communities in Yucatán, Mexico.

Map showing the location of participating communities (black triangles) within the municipalities of Yaxcabá (orange) and Chankom (red). Mérida, the state capital (yellow), is included to illustrate its geographic distance from the study sites, highlighting potential barriers to specialized healthcare access. Communities: Xkalakdzonot (C1), Xcopteil (C2), Ticimul (C3) and Yaxunah (C4) The inset map shows the position of Yucatán within Mexico.

Supplementary table 1. Description of the questionnaires utilized in the census.

Name of the questionnaire	Description of the questionnaire	Measured variables
Sociodemographic	This tool assesses the general characteristics of the population.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Age ● Gender ● Residency place ● Self-ascription as an Indigenous person ● Marital status ● Years of study ● Spoken language (Spanish and/or Mayan-Yucatecan) ● Literacy (Spanish and Mayan-Yucatecan) ● Number of children
Housing Characteristics	This tool assesses the general characteristics, materials and access to services in the house of residency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of people living in the same house ● Number of rooms ● Material of the roof ● Material of the walls ● Material of the floor ● Characteristics of the kitchen ● Combustible used for cooking ● Source of electrical power ● Source and frequency of water ● Characteristics of sewage ● Disposal of trash and solid waste
Clinical measurements	This section measures the clinical outcomes for the most common comorbidities in this population.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capillary glucose (random or fasting) ● Blood pressure ● Weight ● Height ● BMI ● Self-reported comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, others)

COPCORD questionnaire	<p>This tool is used for the screening of RMDs by identifying patients with pain of non-traumatic origin at any time in their lives and/or in the last 7 days. Patients who answer positively to the presence of pain (historically or last 7 days) are considered positive and are subsequently evaluated by rheumatologists to corroborate the final diagnosis of RMDs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● First degree relatives with history of RMDs ● Presence of pain, swelling or stiffness in articulations in the last 7 days ● Presence of pain, swelling or stiffness in articulations in the past ● Number of painful articulations in the body ● Duration of the pain⁺ ● Origin of the pain (traumatic/non-traumatic)⁺ ● Degree of pain⁺ ● Present and past usage of pain medications ● Pain medications (number and names)
<p>Functionality Assessment</p>	<p>This section assesses the degree of independence and the impact of illnesses, pain, or disabilities on individuals ability to work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Work absenteeism ● Length of absenteeism ● Fatigue level in the last month ● Description of non-work related activities ● Affection of the non-work related activities in the last month ● Modifications to the house or work space because of an illness
HAQ-DI questionnaire	<p>Composed of 20 items, it evaluates 8 aspects of daily life: dressing and grooming, rising, eating, walking, hygiene, reaching, grasping, and activities. Each item is scored on a 4-point Likert scale. Disability is determined by calculating the sum of the scores for all categories divided by the number of areas. A score of HAQ-DI positive is defined as >0.8.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Presence of disability (HAQ-DI > 0.8)

Quality of life (EQ-5D)	This instrument measures the subjective quality of life in 5 domains and each domain has 3 levels, also uses a scale to evaluate the overall health state of the person.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mobility ● Personal care ● Daily activities ● Pain/discomfort ● Anxiety/depression ● 4 level Likert scale (binarized into good or bad health state)*
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Questionnaire of health services utilization and socioeconomic impact	It assesses the availability and utilization of health services related to the diseases the person has, the use of medications, patterns of service use, costs, and the quality of care by illness, out-of-pocket expenses, and services used through 61 questions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Type of work ● Salary (per week) ● Governmental allowances ● Utilization of medicines ● Utilization of emergency services ● Utilization of ambulatory attention services ● Cost of transportation to receive health attention ● Out of pocket expenses
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+ These questions are assessed per each painful articulation reported by the patient.

* This scale is a modification from the normal visual analog scale used in EQ-5D-3L because in the Mayan-Yucatecan Indigenous communities a Likert scale works better to represent health states.

Abbreviations: RMDs: rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases; HAQ-DI: Health Assessment Questionnaire-Disability Index; BMI: body mass index; EQ-5D; European Quality of Life-5 Dimensions, COPCORD: Community Oriented Program for the Control of Rheumatic Diseases.

Supplementary material 3. Detailed description of analytical process for the construction and performance of the syndemic index.

Variable definition

The primary binary outcome for regression analyses [1] was the presence of an RMD diagnosis (yes/no).

- **Comorbidities:** binary indicators capturing the presence/absence of each comorbidity.
- **Medications:** a medication table was constructed that included normalized free-text drug names and categorical fields describing prescriber type, source of medication, and payment mode. Categorical prescribing and access variables were one-hot encoded. Total reported medication cost per patient and per wave was also computed.
- **Biomechanical load:** a set of items summarizing work-related and daily-life physical loads (e.g. lifting, pushing, prolonged standing, bending). For each patient and wave, item scores were aggregated to form a biomechanical load profile.
- **Functional status:** measured using EuroQol [2] and HAQ scales [3].
- **Pain:** recent pain (e.g. last 7 days) and longer-term pain were extracted from dedicated tables.
- **Movement assessment:** performance on a battery of tests assessing the ability to carry out specific motor tasks.

To capture multimorbidity around RMD, we defined a **three-level syndemic classification** per patient and wave based on diagnosis and comorbidity status:

1. **No diagnosis:** no RMD diagnosis and no selected comorbidities.
2. **Diagnosis only:** positive RMD diagnosis with no selected comorbidities.
3. **Syndemic:** positive RMD diagnosis plus ≥ 1 selected comorbidity.

In addition, we constructed a **continuous syndemic index** to quantify overall syndemic burden. Variables that showed robust associations with adverse health status in the regression analyses (see below) were first standardized to z-scores and then combined into a weighted composite score, where higher values represent a greater accumulation of negative health and social disadvantages.

Descriptive and cross-sectional analyses

All analyses were performed in Python [4] using pandas [5] and statsmodels [6]; network visualization was conducted in Gephi [7]. Continuous variables were summarized as mean (standard deviation) or median (interquartile range), and categorical variables as counts and percentages.

For categorical variables, we used chi-squared tests (or Fisher's exact tests when expected cell counts were small). For continuous variables, we inspected distributional assumptions and used

either two-sample t-tests or non-parametric tests (Kruskal–Wallis / Wilcoxon rank–sum) as appropriate.

Univariable associations between RMD diagnosis (yes/no) and each candidate predictor were evaluated using the same family of tests (chi-squared/Fisher for categorical variables, parametric or non-parametric two-sample tests for continuous variables). These cross-sectional analyses served as an initial screening for variables associated with RMD diagnosis at baseline and follow-up. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Multivariable logistic regression

To identify independent predictors of RMD diagnosis, we fitted multivariable logistic regression models. Binary predictors were coded as 0/1; continuous predictors were standardized where necessary; and categorical predictors were represented by dummy variables. Variables exhibiting complete or quasi-complete separation were excluded from multivariable models.

ORs with 95% CIs and p-values were derived from model coefficients and used to construct forest-plot style summaries. Variables that remained significantly associated with diagnosis and that reflected adverse health or social conditions were subsequently selected as components of the continuous syndemic index.

Network and cluster analyses

To explore structural patterns in the distribution of syndemic characteristics, we constructed a similarity-based network where each node represented an individual participant. Edges between pairs of participants reflected similarity in their health and social attributes. For continuous variables, pairwise similarity was derived from Euclidean distances; for binary and categorical variables, similarity was derived from the Jaccard index.

Using Gephi force atlas 2 to resolve the network and to the resulting node position we applied the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) [8] algorithm to identify clusters of individuals with similar profiles. Clusters consisting of a single individual (DBSCAN outliers) were excluded from comparative analyses.

For each remaining cluster, we computed summary statistics (cluster size, centroid, mean values of continuous variables, and prevalence of binary variables) and described cluster profiles in terms of sociodemographic characteristics, comorbidity patterns, biomechanical exposures, functional limitations, and syndemic index values.

The resulting networks and clusters were visualized and inspected in Gephi to aid interpretation of syndemic patterns and vulnerability profiles in the study population.

Supplementary figure 2. Methodological diagram of the construction of the syndemic index.

Supplementary figure 3. Syndemic analysis model.

Variables included in the analysis model. Abbreviations: RMD, Rheumatic and Musculoskeletal Diseases; HAQ-Di: Health Assessment Questionnaire- Disability Index; EuroQoL: European Quality of Life-5.

Supplementary figure 4. Methodological diagram of network analysis.

Supplementary table 2. Table of overall differences among variables between clusters

Variable N = 507	<i>P</i>
Sociodemographic	
Age	0.008
Gender	0.323
Schooling	< 0.001
Number of children	< 0.001
Spanish speakers	0.006
Spanish writers	< 0.001
Mayan speakers	0.595
People in household	> 0.99
Clinical	
Acute Pain (< 7 days)	< 0.001
Historic pain (> 7 days)	< 0.001
Family history of RMD	0.061
Incapacity (HAQ-DI >8.0)	< 0.001
Capillary glucose	> 0.99
Systolic blood pressure	0.002
Diastolic blood pressure	< 0.001
RMDs	< 0.001
High blood pressure	< 0.001
Diabetes	0.013
Depression	> 0.99
Pain medication usage	< 0.001
Quality of life, EQ-5D score	0.007
Economic	
Hours of work per day	0.120
Weekly income	0.003
Transportation costs	< 0.001
Owens a motorcycle	< 0.001
Internet service	< 0.001

RMDs: rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases; HAQ-DI: Health Assessment Questionnaire-Disability Index; EQ-5D; European Quality of Life-5 Dimensions
 Tests: Chi-squared for categorical variables. ANOVA for continuous variables.

Supplementary table 3. Post hoc comparisons for variables with significant differences across clusters

Variable	Cluster comparison	<i>p value</i> ~
Sociodemographic		
Age	2-0	<0.001
	4-0	0.001
	5-0	0.002
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	<0.001
	6-1	0.003
	3-2	<0.001
	5-2	0.03
Years of education	6-3	<0.001
	1-0	0.008
	2-0	<0.001
	4-0	0.009
	5-0	0.004
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	<0.001
	3-2	<0.001
Number of children	4-2	0.001
	5-2	<0.001
	6-2	0.025
	6-3	0.005
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	0.006
	4-0	0.007
	6-0	<0.001
Spanish speakers	2-1	0.002
	3-2	0.008
	5-2	0.01
Spanish writers	2-0	<0.001
	2-1	0.016
	3-2	0.003
	2-0	<0.001
	4-0	0.022
	6-0	0.02
	2-1	<0.001
Acute Pain (< 7 days)	3-2	<0.001
	5-2	<0.001
	6-2	0.031
	1-0	<0.001
Acute Pain (< 7 days)	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	0.005
	Clinical	

	6-0	<0.001
	3-1	0.023
	5-1	<0.001
	3-2	<0.001
	5-2	<0.001
	5-4	<0.001
	6-5	<0.001
	1-0	0.007
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	1-0	0.007
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	<0.001
Historic pain (> 7 days)	3-1	<0.001
	4-1	<0.001
	5-1	<0.001
	6-1	<0.001
	3-2	<0.001
	4-2	0.009
	6-2	<0.001
	5-3	<0.001
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	1-0	<0.001
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	<0.001
Incapacity (HAQ-DI >8.0)	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
	2-0	<0.001
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	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	<0.001
	3-1	<0.001
Systolic blood pressure	4-1	<0.001
	6-1	<0.001
	3-2	<0.001
	4-3	<0.001
	5-3	<0.001
	6-3	<0.001
	6-5	<0.001
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	3-0	0.041
Diastolic blood pressure	6-1	0.046
	3-2	0.039
	6-3	<0.001
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	2-0	0.003
	3-0	<0.001
RMDs	4-0	0.001
	6-0	0.002
	3-1	<0.001
	3-2	0.14

	5-3	<0.001
	5-4	0.039
	2-0	0.004
	3-0	<0.001
	3-1	0.01
	2-0	0.001
Hypertension	5-0	0.048
	3-2	<0.001
	5-3	0.034
Diabetes	2-0	0.048
	3-2	0.003
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
Pain medication usage	2-1	<0.001
	3-1	<0.001
	4-1	<0.001
	5-1	<0.001
	6-1	<0.001
	3-2	<0.001
	5-3	0.001
	1-0	<0.001
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	0.014
	3-1	0.013
	5-1	0.019
EQ-5D score <i>mean</i> (SD)	6-1	0.023
	5-2	<0.001
	5-3	<0.001
	5-4	0.003
	6-5	<0.001
Economic		
Weekly income	2-0	0.002
	2-1	0.001
	3-2	<0.001
	4-2	0.01
	6-2	0.006
	1-0	<0.001
	2-0	<0.001
Transportation costs	3-0	<0.001
	4-0	<0.001
	5-0	<0.001
	6-0	<0.001
	2-1	0.001
Owns a motorcycle	5-1	0.27
	3-2	<0.001

	5-3	0.03
	2-0	<0.001
	3-0	0.004
	2-1	<0.001
Internet service	3-1	0.009
	3-2	<0.001
	4-2	<0.001
	5-2	<0.001
	6-2	<0.001
	5-3	<0.001
	6-5	0.005

RMDs: rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases; HAQ-DI: Health Assessment Questionnaire-Disability Index; BMI: body mass index; EQ-5D; European Quality of Life-5 Dimensions.
 Tests: Tukey's HSD for ANOVA; pairwise proportion tests with Bonferroni correction for Chi-squared

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